

ОЦІНКА ТАЗОВОГО ДНА У ЖІНОК ЗА ДОПОМОГОЮ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОГО ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ

ULTRASOUND INVESTIGATION IN THE ASSESSMENT OF THE PELVIC BOTTOM IN WOMEN

Кухта А.О.
Kukhta AO

Науковий керівник: к. мед. н. **Олійник Н. С.**

Scientific adviser: Ph.D. **Oliynyk NS**

Запорізький державний медичний університет

Кафедра акушерства і гінекології

м. Запоріжжя, Україна

Zaporizhzhia State Medical University

Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology

Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine

e-mail: angel.kukhta00@gmail.com

The aim of the study. Assess the diagnostic value of ultrasound in the diagnosis of pelvic floor insufficiency in women.

Materials and methods. Ultrasound examination was performed on 30 women. The mean age of women was 27.8 ± 3.87 years. In the main groups, there were also women who gave birth through natural birth canals. _ The control group is women who have not given birth. All patients had not previously been diagnosed with pelvic floor insufficiency (hereinafter NTD) by vaginal examination, nor did they complain of NTD. Ultrasound was performed on a Voluson E 8, vaginal probe. During the study, the patient occupied a dorsal lithotomy position, hip joints removed, and knee joints bent. The sensor was located transperineally between the pubic bone and the anal margin. Measurements were performed at rest and under strain (Valsalva test). The following parameters were evaluated: height of the perineal tendon center, levator thickness m. Bulbocavernosus and m. Puborectalis, ureterovesical angle (angle L), the presence of cystocele and rectocele.

The results were obtained. The urgency of the NTD problem is due to its wide prevalence, early manifestation, and high frequency of recurrences that do not tend to decrease. According to the results of the ultrasound study, the most indicative parameter is the ureterovesical angle, which was 1.1 times greater in patients of the main group at rest and almost 1.5 times higher than the value of the stress control group (38.61 ± 21.56 against $29.7 \pm 9,925$ the most common degrees). Hypermobility of the urethra was detected in 25% of women who gave birth (Valsalva test angle L = 38.61 ± 21.56 degrees), and in 25% - cystocele (displacement of the posterior wall of the bladder below the pubic joint). In 100% of patients who did not give birth to the angle L at rest and at the Valsalva test within normal limits (23.03 ± 9.93). Thus, in 80% of the studied patients, the criteria of pelvic floor norms were preserved, such as lack of visualization of the cervix below the pubic joint, the height of the perineal tendon center not less than 10 mm (10.2 ± 2.29 mm), a width of muscle bundles "Levator

legs" not less than 10 mm (11.4 ± 3.019 mm) and the absence of muscle diastase in the tendon center.

Conclusions. Ultrasound examination has a high prognostic value in women who do not clinically express complaints and vaginal examination does not show signs of NTD.